

VALKYRIES

D4.4 VALKYRIES harmonisations on first aid technologies and equipment

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable D4.4 aims at:

1. To analyse the compliance of System Requirements defined in D2.7 with the VALKYRIES objectives and achieved results described in WP4 deliverables.
2. Based on the commonly agreed upon among the leaders of WP4, WP5, and WP6 methodology to analyse the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats of each prioritised harmonisation opportunity.
3. To present in detail the VALKYRIES approach for implementation of the suggested opportunity.
4. To formulate some suggestions and recommendations regarding harmonising first aid preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration in cross-border MCI.

(Common points through deliverables)

Due to the horizontality of the project at this stage and the similarities in work packages 4, 5, and 6, a common work methodology has been established for them. This allows to intercompare results between work packages, to be efficient, and to provide a holistic result.

For these reasons, a common Table of Content (TOC) has been established for deliverables 4.4, 5.4, and 6.4. Some chapters are common to these deliverables, which is why they are marked in their title as (common).

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: VALKYRIES harmonisations on first aid preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration

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3. Introduction

In emergency situations, it is critical to have a clear view of available opportunities to make informed decisions and effectively coordinate response efforts. However, identifying and harmonising these opportunities can be challenging in dynamic and changing environments. In this paper, we will explore using SWOT ("strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats") to assess opportunities in emergency situations and the importance of harmonising these opportunities in emergency response. We will also examine some strategies and best practices for addressing the challenges of identifying and coordinating opportunities in emergency response environments.

3.1 Objective (common)

The primary objective of the VALKYRIES project is to develop, implement, validate, and apply innovative theoretical foundations, methods, prototypes, and their demonstration on a reference integration for supporting the ongoing/planned European actions for pre-standardisation and harmonisation technologies, procedures, preparedness, and cross-sector/border cooperation for first aid response at disaster management by emergency health services, with the focus on their vehicular deployments.

To achieve this primary objective and address the challenges identified above, VALKYRIES establishes 9 specific and measurable objectives that are introduced below:

- **VALK-OBJ-1 (Map of growing commercial and R&D opportunities):** Analyse the existing/ongoing technological, procedural, education, and collaborative opportunities of the first aid response supplier markets and related signs of progress beyond the state-of-the-art able to improve the EU disaster resiliency.
- **VALK-OBJ-2 (Sustainable Regulation and ethical compliance):** Analyse the first aid response cross-sector, cross-border, and cross-hierarchy regulatory and ethical principles, identifying minimum standard requirements, lacunae, and hurdles, and developing recommendations to policymakers and stakeholders to facilitate their enforcement through the consolidation of a harmonised regulatory framework and the implementation of new strategic schemes.
- **VALK-OBJ-3 (Sustainable Pre-standardisation and Standardisation):** Research and analyse the pre-standardisation opportunities concerning the first aid response enablers, resulting in recommendations, common requirements, guidelines, and enforcement tools towards constituting a novel and sustainable reference model, being implemented at new standardisation actions.
- **VALK-OBJ-4 (Sustainable certification and conformity assessment criteria):** Analyse the accreditation and certification opportunities concerning the first aid response enablers, including the enforced conformity assessment criteria, evaluation procedures, and facilities, resulting in recommendations, guidelines, and strategies to prompt sustainable certification, accreditation, and homogeneity assessment.
- **VALK-OBJ-5 (Sustainable Harmonisation framework):** Development of a holistic framework for supporting the standardisation/harmonisation of first aid response enablers assuming their cross-sector, cross-border, and cross-hierarchy hybrid dimensions, bearing in mind the vertical/horizontal propagation of consequences of the decisions made between technical, procedural and collaborative domains.

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- **VALK-OBJ-6 (Harmonisation of vehicular first aid technologies, procedures, and collaboration):** Research, analyse, and apply the VALKYRIES' recommendations, guidelines, and harmonisation tactics on reference equipment, technologies, procedures, preparedness, raise awareness and related collaborative solutions.
 - **VALK-OBJ-7 (Cross-sectorial collaboration, civilian protection, volunteering, and military assistance):** Research, analyse and expand the harmonisation framework towards facilitating, guiding, and enhancing the cooperation between vehicular first aid responders with other disaster management actors, among them firefighters, law enforcement agencies, civilian protection, military or heterogeneous volunteering.
 - **VALK-OBJ-8 (Reference integration and interoperation):** Reference integration and interoperation of the harmonised technological, procedural, and collaborative solutions based on the common requirements and gap mitigations prioritised by the committed end-users and practitioners.
 - **VALK-OBJ-9 (Large EU scale cross-border demonstrations):** Evaluation and demonstration of the interoperability and enhancements derived from harmonising vehicular first aid-related enablers at four cross-border and cross-sectorial scenarios: Spain-Portugal, Slovakia-Austria, Bulgaria-Greece, and Norway-Netherlands.

For the scope of deliverable D4.4, to develop the EU-wide roadmap for standardising operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response in multi-casualty disasters, Valkyries researchers defined several requirements related to the various specific objectives the project in (D2.7 Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases).

There are 2 types of requirements regarding WP4 deliverables:

- **Base requirements:** requirements extracted from the description of the tasks in the DoW (technical proposal) of the Valkyries Project. They are considered mandatory.
- **Common requirements:** are those requirements that are not explicitly described in the DoW (therefore considered as extended requirements) but are adopted by agreement between the Project partners. They are optional requirements.

VALKYRIES adopts the following requirements prioritisation scale:

- **P1 (Highest priority):** Priority requirements must be met for the system not to fail. They will be partially covered by functionalities verified in the previous verification and validation processes. The fulfilment of the requirement may condition the progress toward the fulfilment of the P2 priority conditions.
- **P2 (Moderate priority):** P2 requirements must be fulfilled once P1 requirements have been satisfied. The requirements will be partially covered by functionalities verified in the intermediate verification and validation processes.
- **N/A (Not Applicable):** The requirement shall be considered from the very beginning (by design).

Finally, the methods to verify and validate the requirements are Demonstration, Analysis, Test, Inspection, and Special Qualification Methods (any other verification procedure).

3.1.1 Expert consultation

The results of the harmonisation and pre-standardisation tasks have been subjected to internal validation processes with the most expert project researchers in each case, consultation with

the External Advisory Board (EAB), and, in some cases, external validation with experts from outside the project.

3.2 Requirements compliance matrix

The description of the requirements can be consulted in deliverable D2.7 (1). The following table lists the requirements related to deliverable D4.4 and their traceability to the Valkyries project objectives.

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T4.1_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D4.1/D4.5 D4.2/D4.6 D4.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION Opportunities is presented in D4.1,/D4.5 D4.2/D4.3. Road Map in D4.3
REQ_BASE_T4.1_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D4.1/D4.5 D4.2/D4.6 D4.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION Opportunities is presented in D4.1,/D4.5 D4.2/D4.3. Road Map in D4.3
REQ_BASE_T4.1_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D4.1/D4.5 D4.2/D4.6 D4.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION Opportunities is presented in D4.1,/D4.5 D4.2/D4.3. Road Map in D4.3
REQ_BASE_T4.1_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D4.1/D4.5 D4.2/D4.6 D4.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION Opportunities is presented in D4.1,/D4.5 D4.2/D4.3. Road Map in D4.3
REQ_BASE_T4.1_5	P1	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.1/D4.5 D4.2/D4.6	REQUIRED	INSPECTION Result presented in D4.1,/D4.5 D4.2/D4.3
REQ_BASE_T4.1_6	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.3,D7-8	REQUIRED	Test. Will be demonstrated in User cases primarily UC4
REQ_BASE_T4.2_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.1/D4.5 D4.2/D4.6 D4.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION Gaps, opportunities, and roadmap are presented in D4.1/D4.5, D4.2/D4.6, and D4.3
REQ_BASE_T4.2_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D2.8 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The designed architecture will be demonstrated in D7.3

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
		VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9			
REQ_COM_T4.2_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.1/D4.5 D2.8 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The communication capabilities of devices to share data between them and SIGRUN will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.2_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.1/D4.5 D4.2/D4.6 D4.3 D4.4 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The common technologies for communication in the emergency scenario will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.2_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.1/D4.5 D4.2/D4.6	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The best communication technologies depending on the data that need to be sent were analysed in D4.1/D4.5 and D4.2/D4.6
REQ_COM_T4.2_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D7.3	RECOMMENDED	DEMONSTRATION The communication between devices and SIGRUN will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.2_5	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.4 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The sending of confidential data between devices will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.2_6	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D6.4 D7.3	RECOMMENDED	DEMONSTRATION The guarantee of the integrity of the exchange data between devices will be demonstrated in D7.3.

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
		VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9			
REQ_COM_T4.2_7	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.2/D4.6 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The accessibility and continuity of data exchange between devices will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.2_8	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The authentication of devices will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.2_9	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The use of roles will be demonstrated for each network will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.2_10	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The use of optimisation mechanisms by the system will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.2_11	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D4.2/D4.6 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The deployment of a redundant system will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.2_12	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D6.4 D7.3	RECOMMENDED	DEMONSTRATION The use of encryption techniques when storing data will be demonstrated in D7.3

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_COM_T4.2_13	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D4.2/D4.6 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The use of trust scores between parties will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.2_14	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.2/D4.6 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The use of gateways and connectivity between different communication technologies will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.2_15	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D4.2/D4.6	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The use of different priority communication channels was analysed in D4.2/D4.6
REQ_COM_T4.2_16	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The use of network and communication infrastructure efficiently and fast deployable will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.2_17	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.3	REQUIRED	TEST INSPECTION The use of blockchain to keep the integrity of data exchange will be tested in D7.3
REQ_BASE_T4.3_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8	D.4.4 D.7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST The roadmaps related to opportunities are described in D.4.4 and validated in D.7.3.
REQ_BASE_T4.3_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6	REQUIRED	INSPECTION State of the art is defined in D.4.1/D4.5 and gaps and opportunities identified in D.4.2 /D.4.6

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T4.3_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.3 D.4.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION Gaps and opportunities are analysed in D.4.2/D4.6, D4.3, and in D.4.4, the SWOT for the selected harmonization opportunities is carried out
REQ_BASE_T4.3_4	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.3 D.4.4	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The roadmap of the selected harmonization opportunities is described in D.4.4, and the initial state of the art is done in D.4.1/D.4.5
REQ_BASE_T4.3_5	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.3 D.4.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST The roadmaps are described in D.4.4 and validated and tested in D.7.3, and demonstrators
REQ_COM_T4.3_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.3 D.4.4 D.7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST The real-time updating will be validated in D.7.3 and demonstrators, also related to opportunities analysed in D.4.3 and D.4.4 and included in architecture design D.2.8
REQ_COM_T4.3_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.3 D.4.4 D.7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST The multiplatform requirement will be tested in D.7.3 and is analysed in deliverables associated with state of the art (D.4.1/D.4.5), gaps and opportunities (D.4.2/D.4.6/D.4.3), and Architecture Design (D.2.8)

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_COM_T4.3_3	P3	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The architecture takes into account this requirement concerning satellite communications of the C&C system (D.2.8) and additionally analyses the deliverables related to the state of the art and gaps and opportunities (D.4.1/D.4.5/D4.2/D.4.6)
REQ_COM_T4.3_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D4.6 D.4.3 D.4.4 D.7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The requirement related to the usability of applications is cross-cutting for all deliverables and is addressed both in the gaps and in the final harmonisation opportunities (D.4.1/D.4.5, D4.2/D.4.6, D.4.3, D.4.4) and validated in D.7.3 and demonstrators
REQ_COM_T4.3_5	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST The requirement related to Data Synchronization is included in the architecture design in D.2.8 and validated in D.7.3
REQ_COM_T4.3_6	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The requirement is contemplated in the architecture design (D.2.8) and considered in the initial state of the art and gap analysis (D.4.1/D.4.5, D.4.2/D.4.6) TEST NOT PURSUED
REQ_COM_T4.3_7	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST The requirement related

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
			D.4.4 D.7.3		to Data Refresh is an architecture requirement (D.2.8) and is validated in D.7.3, and demonstrators
REQ_COM_T4.3_8	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.3 D.4.4 D.7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST The communication between wearables and the C&C centre is included in the architecture deliverable (D.2.8) and validated in D.7.3 and demonstrators. Also, there is a specific opportunity Roadmap related to wearables (D.4.1 /D4.5, D.4.2/D.4.6, D.4.3, D.4.4)
REQ_COM_T4.3_9	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.4 D.7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST The requirement related to Sensitive Data Encryption is an architecture requirement (D.2.8) and is validated in D.7.3, and demonstrators
REQ_COM_T4.3_10	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.4 D.7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION TEST SIGRUN platform provides a common architecture to share information between countries in an agile way. The requirement is included in D.2.8 and validated in D.7.3, and demonstrators
REQ_COM_T4.3_11	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.4 D.7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION TEST The requirement related to sensors Integration is an architecture requirement (D.2.8) and also is analysed in state

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
					of the art analysis (D.4.1/D.4.5), gaps and opportunities (D.4.2/D4.6) TEST Not pursued
REQ_COM_T4.3_12	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST The requirement related to Confirmation states is an architecture requirement (D.2.8) validated in D.7.3 and demonstrators
REQ_COM_T4.3_13	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.1/D.4.5 D.7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION TEST The engine GIS requirements are included in D.2.8 and validated in D.7.3. The state-of-the-art Deliverable (D.4.1/D.4.5) also analyses standards and technological options for this functionality.
REQ_COM_T4.3_14	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.4 D.7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The relevant information on the incident storage was used in D4.3 and D4.4. It will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.3_15	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.1/D.4.6	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The requirement is included in the Architecture Design (D.2.8) and state of the art analysis (D.4.1/D.4.6) TEST NOT PURSUED
REQ_COM_T4.3_16	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The architecture design includes external sources of information

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
					(D.2.8) and SIGRUN platform implementation will be tested in D.7.3 and demonstrators
REQ_COM_T4.3_17	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.4 D.7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION Critical infrastructure information can be easily incorporated into C&C systems. This is defined in the architecture deliverable and will be validated in the 7.3 demonstrators
REQ_COM_T4.3_18	P2	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.4 D.7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST Specific dashboards for decision support will be used in the final demonstrators. These Dashboards will be validated in D.7.3, demonstrators (WP7) and previously have been defined in architecture design (D.2.8)
REQ_COM_T4.3_19	P2	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.4 D.7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION: The design of data exchange supports the requirement (see D2.8) TEST: To be tested in D.7.3 and WP7 demos.
REQ_COM_T4.3_20	P2	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.4 D.7.3	RECOMMENDED	TEST To be tested in WP7 demos
REQ_COM_T4.3_21	P2	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The requirement related to medical data requests is contemplated in the architecture design and taken into account in the initial state of the art and gap analysis

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
					(D.4.1/D.4.5 and D.4.2/D.4.6) TEST NOT PURSUED
REQ_COM_T4.3_22	P2	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D.2.8 D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.3 D.4.4 D.7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION: The design of data exchange supports the requirement (see D2.8) and is related to the final harmonization opportunities (D.4.1/D.4.5, D.4.2/D.4.6, D.4.3/D.4.4) TEST: To be tested in WP7 demos and D.7.3.
REQ_BASE_T4.4_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.4 D.7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION State of the art related to digital twins and BMI is explored in D.4.1/D4.5 and is an architecture design requirement (D.2.8) TEST To be tested in D.7.3 and WP7 demos.
REQ_BASE_T4.4_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.3 D.4.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The regulatory aspects of technological harmonisation are explored in D.4.2/D4.6 and D.4.3 , D.4.4
REQ_COM_T4.4_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The recommendation for the use of AI to suggest evacuation routes is included in the deliverables and addressed in both the gaps and final harmonisation opportunities in D.4.1/D.4.5. TEST NOT PURSUED

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_COM_T4.4_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The recommendation for use of AI to suggest priority of evacuation of victims is included in the deliverables and addressed in both the gaps and final harmonisation opportunities in D.4.1/D.4.5. TEST NOT PURPUSED
REQ_COM_T4.4_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The use of AI to prioritise the evacuation process is explored in D.4.1/ D4.5, D.4.2/D.4.6 TEST NOT PURPUSED
REQ_COM_T4.4_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The use of AI to prioritise the evacuation process is explored in D4.1 TEST NOT PURPUSED
REQ_COM_T4.4_5	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.3 D.4.4 D.7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION State of the art related to digital twins and BMI is explored in D.4.1/ D4.5, D.42/D.4.6 TEST To be tested in D.7.3 and WP7 demos and also is defined in Architecture D.2.8
REQ_COM_T4.4_6	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.2.8 D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION DTI (Digital Twins Instance) is explored in D.4.1/D.4.5, D.4.2/D.4.6) and included in architecture design (D.2.8)

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_COM_T4.4_7	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.2.8	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION DTA (Digital Twins Aggregated) is explored in D.4.1/D.4.5, D.4.2/D.4.6) and included in architecture design (D.2.8)
REQ_COM_T4.4_8	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.2.8	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The Portable Digital Twins (EDT) requirement is explored in D.4.1/D.4.5, D.4.2/D.4.6) and included in architecture design (D.2.8)
REQ_COM_T4.4_9	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The recommendation related to Augmented Reality Visualisation is collateral to all deliverables and is addressed both in the gaps and in the final harmonisation opportunities D.4.1/D.4.5 and D.4.3
REQ_COM_T4.4_10	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.3 D.4.4 D.7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The requirement related to VCSM (victim case management system) is included in all deliverables and is addressed both in the gaps and in the final harmonisation opportunities D.4.1/D.4.5 ,D.4.2/D.4.6 ,D.4.3 ,D.4.4.4 To be tested in D.7.3 and WP7 demos and also defined in Architecture D.2.8
REQ_COM_T4.4_11	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.3 D.4.4 D.7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST The recommendation regarding wireless communication is

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
					included in all deliverables and is addressed both in the gaps and in the final harmonisation opportunities D.4.1/D.4.5, D.4.3, D.4.4 and D.4.4 is tested in D.7.3 and in WP7 would be demonstrated
REQ_COM_T4.4_12	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D.4.1/D.4.5 D.4.2/D.4.6 D.4.3 D.4.4 D.7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST The recommendation regarding hands-free technology is included in all deliverables and is addressed both in the gaps and in the final harmonisation opportunities D.4.1/D.4.5, D.4.3, D.4.4 and D.4.4 is tested in D.7.3 and in WP7 the demonstration would be done
REQ_BASE_T4.5_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.1/D4.5	REQUIRED	INSPECTION State of the art in the most promising technological alternatives was analysed in D4.1/D4.5
REQ_BASE_T4.5_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.1/D4.5	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The analysis of legal terms based on communication and information transmitted was done in D4.1/D4.5
REQ_BASE_T4.5_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D4.1/D4.5 D4.2/D4.6 D4.3 D4.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The categorisation, selection, and applicability of technologies within the framework were done in D2.8
REQ_COM_T4.5_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5	D2.8 D4.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
		VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.4		The use of portable devices which offer relevant data was analysed in D2.8
REQ_COM_T4.5_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D4.4 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The sending of data between devices and SIGRUN will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.5_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.3 D4.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The portable and lightweight devices will be analysed in D4.3 and D4.4
REQ_COM_T4.5_4	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.3 D4.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The study of good batteries for devices will be done in D4.3 and D4.4
REQ_COM_T4.5_5	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.3 D4.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The study of wearables that easily support the requirements will be done in D4.3 and D4.4
REQ_COM_T4.5_6	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.3 D4.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The study of devices to have sufficient communication range to interconnect with one another will be done in D4.3 and D4.4
REQ_COM_T4.5_7	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.3 D4.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The analysis of devices to incorporate several communication interfaces will be done in D4.3 and D4.4
REQ_COM_T4.5_8	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D4.3 D4.4	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The analysis of device hardware that is easily

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
		VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9			upgradeable will be done in D4.3 and D4.4
REQ_COM_T4.5_9	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.3 D4.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The study of wearables devices capable of obtaining geolocational position will be done in D4.3 and D4.4
REQ_COM_T4.5_10	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.3 D4.4 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The use of an easy configuration of the devices will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.5_11	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.3 D4.4	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The use of wearables easily to use will be demonstrated in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.5_12	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-6	D4.2/D4.6 D7.3	REQUIRED	INSPECTION TEST The use of monitors for first responders' fatigue will be tested in D7.3
REQ_COM_T4.5_13	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.3 D4.4 D7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION Supported in the document architecture D2.8; TEST NOT AVAILABLE
REQ_COM_T4.5_14	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D4.3 D4.4 D7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION Supported in the document architecture D2.8; TEST The use of wearables to share victims' data will be tested in D7.3 First Aid Vehicles sharing data with the victims was not pursued

ID	Priority	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	WBS deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_COM_T4.5_15	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D4.3 D4.4 D7.3	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION Supported in the document architecture D2.8; TEST Victim digital registration tools will be tested in D7.3

Table 1 – WP4 Requirements.

4. Methodology (common)

The methodology for developing the deliverable D4.4 was commonly agreed upon among the leaders of WP4, WP5 and WP6, and it is common for deliverables D5.4 (2) and D6.4 (3). NOVOTEC as framework harmonisation and INDRA as project leader supported this process.

The methodology followed in this deliverable has been to develop the opportunities that the project has arrived at through a logical reasoning process. It can be seen in detail in the deliverables on the harmonisation report.

In this last phase, the VALKYRIES project analyses the opportunities in-depth and realises the first steps of these harmonisations. Building a proposal that will be tested in further stages of the project.

This deliverable is the end of the technical analysis of the opportunities within the project, but it is the beginning of the specific development and can generate future projects.

5. Opportunities analysis

To carry out the pre-standardisation of the opportunities prioritised in deliverable D4.3 (4), we will carry out a SWOT analysis that will help us better understand each opportunity's need and subsequently define the harmonisation process carried out.

5.1 SWOT methodology (common)

SWOT analysis is a technique widely used in business to analyse a situation to make the right strategic decisions.

It is a systematic approach that facilitates analysis by distinguishing between the pros and cons of both the external and internal environment. In this way, 4 areas are defined, which correspond to the acronym SWOT:

- Strengths: They bring together the set of internal resources, positions of power and any competitive advantage specific to the agent under study.
- Weaknesses: Due to its internal characteristics, these aspects limit the development capacity of the agent under study.
- Opportunities: These are any factors external to the agent under study that favour its development or offer the possibility of implementing improvements.
- Threats: These are all the external factors that could prevent the implementation of a strategy or jeopardise the viability of a proposal.

It can be represented graphically in 4 quadrants:

Figure 1 - SWOT matrix.

The project researchers have applied this systematic SWOT approach to assessing the EU environment for each of the top 6 selected clustered opportunities.

Each analysis is preceded by a summary of the current EU landscape encountered in the previous phases of the project and includes a review of the primary harmonisation efforts undertaken to date, all concerning the specific scope of the clustered opportunities assessed.

5.2 CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles

This sub-chapter presents the opportunity CO.WP4.15 of near/nearest vehicles opportunity SWOT analysis and approach followed in VALKYRIES.

5.2.1 SWOT evaluation

Location of near/nearest vehicles opportunity aims to explore the potential of knowing the vehicles position in the MCI event field by the C2 and responders and share such information through the joint forces of different entities. It requires that the functions, technological artefacts and solutions are coherent and interoperable so that the information chains, from positional data generation up to the responders and medical responders, can access such data in due time. The SWOT analysis presented below presents the key elements to consider to achieve the desired functions and operational execution.

5.2.1.1 Strengths

1. Using location information of the responders, ambulances and other emergency vehicles involved in an MCI response allow for a better time response in assisting the victims.
2. Knowing the victim's and vehicle's location enables the command post to better manage the allocation of the vehicles to the victim's needs.
3. Using multiple location artefacts, Galileo/GPS receivers, and cell phones, combined supported in multiple networks infrastructures (4G/5G / satcom / Wi-Fi – WAN) increases the system's resilience to face events that damage the infrastructures.
4. Knowing the location of the response vehicles in detail and in real-time allows the command post to monitor potential hazards or risk situations the vehicles FR may face in fast changing events.
5. By having a real-time position of the vehicle, it is possible to forecast the ETA of the vehicle arriving at the hospital and better time organise the medical staff.

5.2.1.2 Weaknesses

1. Using location information of the responders, ambulances and other emergency vehicles involved in an MCI response depend on the availability of the network, which may be limited access or coverage or also be damaged in significant natural events, preventing the report of the vehicle's location.
2. Not all vehicles have the means and technology to report their position, so the investment is required to upgrade them to use such devices.
3. Integration of the vehicle's location with the external application may be required (For example, hospitals).
4. Some technologies already provide the vehicle's location (TETRA), but its integration with C2 systems is limited.
5. Different forces handle different technologies; therefore, they use the location information in different formats, making more difficult location data sharing.

5.2.1.3 Opportunities

1. Generate location services to inform the response downstream service providers (hospital, medical centres, etc.) with the vehicle's location, ETA to destination, etc.
2. Upgrade response vehicles to incorporate location devices and digital communication capability.
3. Provide vehicles with guidance to collect a victim in a precise position.
4. Harmonise the location and vehicle position format and protocol to a common standard at the EU level.
5. Establish a mechanism to share vehicle location data through a federation of joint-operated entities.

5.2.1.4 Threats

1. Lack of harmonisation of the vehicle's location degrades the cross-entity cooperation and management of the in-filed vehicle's response.
2. The different application technologies already exist by the different EU/National response forces and their legacy obstacles to harmonising location sharing.

5.2.2 Scope of VALKYRIES approach

To address this opportunity, the approach to follow 3 key initiatives:

PROPOSAL OF A HARMONISED NEAR/NEAREST VEHICLES SOLUTION

It was based on the analysis of the use cases and the needs set out in the requirements. Being identified as a critical requirement, the design of the information-sharing mechanism of VALKYRIES (SIGRUN) took into consideration these needs and the opportunity (See deliverable D2.8 (5)).

The harmonisation development approach followed the following steps, as per established in the D2.8 - Architecture:

1. Analysis of the use cases.
2. Identify the technologies, technological artefacts, and services already used by the forces involved in the use cases.
3. Designing the models that support the data chain, from the data (position location) generation, the connectivity and network interoperability solution, and the data models that support the data exchange.
4. Analysis of the taxonomies data standards applicable to the MCI events.
5. Generation of a Minimum Data Set to adopt in the data sharing model, including I,) the location data: II) the organisation and assets data, III) the sharing mechanisms and IV) the metadata that supports the orchestration of the information management.
6. It defined the services to support the data sharing and the protocols to use.
7. Defining the tools API enables the users' application to share (publish or consume) the vehicle's location data (as well as other assets and personnel location data).

Note: for a detailed description of the approach implementation and outcome, please refer to deliverable D2.8.

IMPLEMENT AND DEMO THE SOLUTION

From the design developed, the implementation followed by establishing the details of the VALKYRIES model and adapting the critical application to implement the data chain flow. For

that purpose, the technological partners and their proposed solutions were adapted to comply with the API and data model defined by VALKYRIES.

Each application manages the translation from the VALKYRIES location data and data model into its own internal structure for that purpose.

To evaluate the OP.WP4.15 opportunity solutions implemented, the trials and validation will be conducted in several phases and finally demonstrated and assessed on the simulacrum according to WP7. When possible, and existing vehicles with location capability, their location information will be used to validate the data flow chain from the vehicle to the C2 / COP system.

PROMOTE THE SOLUTION ACROSS THE POTENTIAL END USERS AND INDUSTRY

The expected result for this opportunity is that their benefits will outweigh the costs for integration and that END-USER and potential INDUSTRY players may adopt, in the future, the solution developed. Therefore, the WP3: task 3.6- Sustainable exploitation and commercial deployment, will address the OP.WP4.15 results from a commercial perspective and complement, when feasible, with commercial add-ons to the solution design towards an easy adoption by the MCI events response community.

5.2.3 Conclusions

The core of the opportunity is about standardisation and harmonisation of the technological chain that supports the usage and exploitation of the locations of the vehicle in assisting victims, optimising the global response and better managing the medical support and response to victims. It implies that the chain covers the GNSS generation data of the vehicles location, the data reporting to the central system and the data models that support the sharing of its location with the users in need of that information and will benefit from the information of the vehicle ETA, such as hospitals and medical centres that provide the medical response. Therefore, a common semantic and taxonomy should be standardised; the key technological artefacts and components should be interoperable; the location data sharing mechanisms should be standardised in a standard data model, and a common framework, including the API, should be established.

Guidelines: Sharing vehicles position in MCI events, enables a better management of the situational response. Solution should cover the interoperability through the whole data flow, from the location devices (GNSS) up to the data sharing mechanisms. Particular attention require the cases where coverage is missing or poorly supported, where satellite communications aid could be a potential alternative solution.

Vehicles data sharing between joint forces organizations should be available as each organization should remain independent only sharing the location of the shared assets.

Standardizes data taxonomy and semantics should be achieved.

Lessons learnt:

Vehicles tracking and location application can adopt the Valkyries Framework. The sharing of the position requires already available tools to provide additional function to managed information from external assets; Vehicles assets availability and workflows will need to be incorporated in the managing application based on federated concepts, not on single structure/organization models.

5.3 CO.WP4.28: Cross-border data trace

This sub-chapter presents the opportunity CO.WP4.28 related to cross-border data trace as an opportunity for SWOT analysis and approach followed in VALKYRIES.

5.3.1 SWOT evaluation

Tracing data in the cross-border incident is only achievable through official data exchange between authorities following bi-lateral agreements between countries.

As so, even vital data could be necessary for decision-making between Civil protection Agencies in cross-border incidents with many casualties, and they need to be restricted due to national and international agreements and laws.

As this is a primary obstacle in today's C2s of Civil Protection Agencies' operations in cross-border disasters, no system sharing data is available today, leaving all coordination or synchronisation to voice communications or other mechanisms that cannot support data tracing.

The system architecture of SIGRUN introduced in the VALKYRIES project allows the secure and GDPR-compliant exchange of data between different agencies within the same country or between different countries. Using COP exchange, all allowed information by bi-lateral agreements between neighbour countries involved in cross-border disasters can be exchanged as valuable data for handling from the receiving agency.

5.3.1.1 Strengths

1. Easy to implement different syntheses of federated systems in each country, mapping their tactical information to COPs that are exchanged within the country. Every decision maker has the same tactical information from all types of info (from federated systems or external resources).
2. Easy to filter information that is considered confidential for sharing with foreign authorities.
3. COP sharing of information allows tracing data in cross-border disasters to synchronise decision-making following different rescue or response plans.
4. Common teams of rescuers are possible, as they must follow the commands of an authority on the field and national instructions and guidelines.
5. Synchronisation, homogenisation, and finally, standardisation of risk and rescue plans are possible due to the "lessons learned" valuation activities following the execution of a plan. As such, data tracing, as per VALKYRIES/SINGRUN architecture, also collects valuable knowledge from other countries.
6. Well-defined workflows of the Valkyries/SIGRUN operational centre that can be used.

5.3.1.2 Weaknesses

1. Different technologies of various devices, data accessibility and COPs are already in use. Typical COPs are not designed to operate with data-sharing concepts with other countries in mind.
2. Medical personnel trust only devices from medical equipment manufacturers and medical data authorised by their authorities. As so, relevant data are to be considered with minimum trust.

5.3.1.3 Opportunities

1. Introducing a path for standardisation and homogenisation of procedures and workflows in planning, response, and decision-making after data exchange in cross-border disasters.
2. Create common trust between authorities.
3. Exchange knowledge, experiences and lessons learned through data tracing and COP sharing.

5.3.1.4 Threats

1. Low acceptance of shared data by medical or paramedical personnel and authorities.
2. Bioethical issues may be different between countries.

5.3.2 Scope of VALKYRIES approach

Valkyries SINGRUN architecture allows alternative sensing devices or technologies to support the first responders' mission, triage procedures on victims included.

PROCESS ANALYSIS AND PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

The first step is to analyse the current situation and understand why data are not traced or shared and used today in rescue during disasters to support triage or other crucial functions. The following factors are identified:

1. Lack of industry's common standards in closed architecture non-federated COP systems. As every company producing COPs used in triage and tactical data mapping support or use preparatory protocols or data sets, exchanging such information between agencies in multicausality disaster events is difficult.
2. Lack of alternative communication channels: if the people involved in the resolution of the emergency don't have access to the means to obtain or report information, they surely resort to voice calls or other analogue media, resulting in low performance and effectiveness of first responders. as it happens today between different C2 centres.
3. Training of the civilian population on how to handle emergency situations: if the civilian population does not have a public means through which to receive information or does not know how to use the available resources to obtain said information, they will rely on fake news or other untrusted sources of information as the main source of information, or they will rely on social media uncontrolled information spreading.

STRATEGY TO ADDRESS THE OPPORTUNITY

There are various strategies with the aim of data exchanges between C2 during emergency management between the different actors involved, considering the factors exposed in the previous section. One of the main objectives should be to improve the availability and accuracy of the information in emergency management. The following possible solutions should be considered in the Valkyries as one of the main opportunities towards standardisation and harmonisation:

1. Sharing information between agencies of the different countries involved in the emergency improves the coordination of actions to manage the incident. Therefore, cooperative work between countries and sharing information and resources helps to obtain a complete picture of the situation and make more effective decisions.
2. Collect information in almost real-time (such as the status of the injured, the situation of assets and people, or information on the progress of the cause of the natural disaster

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- or information on the consequences of the disaster) and have it in the IT systems available and shared by the agencies and authorities, helps identify the most affected areas and direct resources more effectively.
3. Establishment of clear and standardised protocols for data handling and exchange through the Valkyries SIGRUN architecture.
 4. Information gateways allow the automatic integration of the updated and real-time position of the victims or the vehicles through GIS/Galileo systems to know the location and situation of all victims and assets on the ground and coordinate the assignment of pending dispatch tasks.
 5. Standardisation of the data model allows interoperability, and it is feasible to share and use them between different systems and organisations so that they can be compatible after a transformation process with the applications used for management command and control.
 6. Close to real-time exchange of tactical or weather information from different external sources bring more information to decision makers in a C2 centre if they know the decision maker's view from the other side of the border.
 7. Usual solidarity requests between countries are better understood when data are exchanged.
 8. Alarm and Warnings effects on the general population can be more successful following fake news or other responses in (no-bordered) social media.

ACTION PLAN

The steps to be followed that make up the action plan are described:

1. Create a global scheme for the information that can be shared between the C2s and countries, allowing more efficient emergency tracking, tracing and management of victims supporting triage. This is at the core of the VALKYRIES project, as materialised with SIGRUN architecture.
2. Proof of concept using the above combination of technologies based on COP sharing in different uses/scenarios within the Valkyries project.
3. Use wearables to support evacuated victims moving between countries by tracking, tracing, and management.
4. Create a first consensus from at least one EU country to accept such a method to support triage as a pre-standard primarily.
5. Publish the evidenced measurable results from Valkyries UCs testing this opportunity against the non-use of data traceability through COP sharing.

5.3.3 Conclusions

The core of the opportunity is about standardisation and harmonisation of the technological chain that supports COP sharing as the basic mechanism for data tracing in cross-border disasters. The benefits of using Valkyries/SIGRUN architecture as a standard during disasters also create a major opportunity for EU industries to support systems building COPs against their competition. Therefore, a common semantic and taxonomy should be standardised; the key technological artefacts and components should be interoperable; and the location or vital data sharing mechanisms should be standardised in a common data model and a common framework, including the API to existing systems or apps supporting victims' management and handling, should be established.

5.4 CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges

The opportunity to reduce voice communications and reduce workload has a direct impact on improving emergency management by COPs, but to be implemented, it needs to:

1. Command and control applications must be sufficiently interoperable to integrate this data and send real-time information.
2. To have robust communications systems that allow reliable transmission of information in situations where bandwidth is more limited (areas with poor coverage or specific problems in emergencies) or even absent due to the collapse of all terrestrial networks. In such a case, COPs from neighbour countries could be useful in saving lives.

The implementation proposed by VALKYRIES provides an architecture that facilitates the adaptation and creation of new applications based on this paradigm. There are already standard protocols related to emergency management (EDXL), and they are included in the architecture model. However, the design of SIGRUN goes a step further in this sense. It makes it possible to guarantee a federated model of interoperability between systems in different Countries and Agencies that allows the creation of additional applications and services related to Emergency Management that allow sharing of information more agilely and improve the decision-making process in critical situations.

5.4.1.1 Strengths

1. Reducing voice communication and using applications that digitise information and reduce manual data entry directly impact the efficiency of emergency management.
2. Having digital information available facilitates the traceability of emergency management and allows for a posteriori analysis of this data to improve processes.
3. An integrated application with real-time triage data in the Command-and-Control application facilitates decision-making at the command post.
4. Having the information digitised facilitates the exchange of information between countries.
5. The model defined by VALKYRIES allows existing applications to be adapted and new applications to be developed under this paradigm. The architecture is a high-level platform that allows the connection between applications and services related to Emergency Management, allowing each partner to develop its application according to the model in an open model of application creation.
6. Having a standard between countries facilitates the exchange of data between countries and between the agencies themselves.
7. Numerous applications are on the market for incident management and task management, creating dashboards that can easily be integrated into C2 applications, thus reducing manual work.

5.4.1.2 Weaknesses

1. In terms of the application design that replaces voice data collection, there is a high dependence on the reliability of the networks; in areas with poor coverage, the systems must be able to operate with reduced bandwidths and be reliable in the event of possible communication outages. They must be able to operate offline and send the information once they have communications.

2. Many agencies have custom-developed applications with few or no integration mechanisms of C2 applications. If data is not shared between agencies, the difficulty is greater when countries are involved.
3. The applications to be developed should have a high level of usability and should be easy to handle in a stressful situation. The user will likely prefer to use conventional voice channels if they are too complex and require too much training.

5.4.1.3 Opportunities

1. The architecture model implemented by VALKYRIES (VALKYRIES Interoperability Framework) facilitates the proliferation of new applications that bypass voice communications and allow data to be digitised.
2. The model is designed to allow the easy addition of IOT devices to facilitate data digitisation and integration.
3. The evolution towards federated platforms and more open interoperability models in the market will facilitate the deployment of such solutions.

5.4.1.4 Threats

1. Command and Control application manufacturers tend to have poorly interoperable and closed end-to-end solutions that do not facilitate third-party integration. They tend to be monolithic applications with few integration options.
2. There is no clear standard, and this makes interoperability between systems difficult.
3. There is still a reluctance to share information between First Responders.
4. Command and Control applications are very focused on the specific needs of an Agency and are not initially designed to share information in an agile way. Adapting legacy systems can be complex technically.

5.4.2 Scope of VALKYRIES approach

To address this opportunity, the following usual steps in the execution of projects will be carried out: process analysis, the definition of objectives, identification of alternatives, establishing an action plan and finally, how we can evaluate the impact of the implementation.

PROCESS ANALYSIS AND PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

The first step is to analyse the current situation and understand why many voice calls occur during emergency management. The following factors are identified:

1. Lack of up-to-date and accurate information: If people don't have clear and up-to-date information about the emergency, they may need to make a phone call to obtain that information, especially if there are different sources of information that may offer conflicting or confusing messages.
2. Lack of alternative communication channels: if the people involved in resolving the emergency don't have access to the means to obtain or report information, they surely resort to voice calls to obtain and report information or help.
3. Training of the civilian population on how to handle emergency situations: if the civilian population does not have a public means to receive information or does not know how to use the available resources to obtain said information, they will resort to voice calls as the main source of information.

STRATEGY TO ADDRESS THE OPPORTUNITY

There are various strategies to reduce voice calls during emergency management between the different actors involved, considering the factors exposed in the previous section.

One of the main objectives should be **to improve the availability and accuracy of the information in emergency management**. The following possible solutions should be considered:

1. Share information between agencies of the different countries involved in the emergency to improve the coordination of actions to manage the incident. Cooperative work between countries and sharing information and resources helps to obtain a complete picture of the situation and make more effective decisions.
2. Collect information on the ground in real-time (such as the status of the injured, the situation of assets and people, or information on the progress of the cause of the natural disaster) and have it in the IT systems available and shared by the agencies and authorities, helps identify the most affected areas and direct resources more effectively.
3. Establishment of clear and standardised protocols. It is important for the collection, analysis, and transmission of information in emergency situations. These protocols must include procedures for verifying and validating the information, as well as for continuously updating data.

Another objective would be to **facilitate communication channels that would allow people and assets on the ground** to notify the command control centre of updated information about their situation and the state of the emergency without the need to do it manually and using a voice call to convey that information to ensure that the information arrives complete and that it is distributed effectively. For this, the usual technologies must be used nowadays:

1. Mobile applications that allow information to be shared in real time between field staff and coordination and response teams.
2. Information gateways allow the automatic integration of the updated and real-time position of the vehicles through GIS, to know the situation of all the assets on the ground and coordinate the assignment of pending dispatch tasks.
3. Standardisation of the data model so that it allows interoperability, and it is feasible to share and use them between different systems and organisations and that they can be compatible after a transformation process with the applications used for management command and control.

ACTION PLAN

The steps to be followed that make up the action plan are described:

1. Creating a global scheme for the information that can be shared between the actors and countries allows more efficient emergency management. The following illustration presents a scheme that shows the information that has been identified and that is considered suitable and feasible to be shared globally.

Figure 2 - Global shared information scheme

- To identify concretely the information coming from the different actors that can be shared between the two countries:

Source	Information
Vehicles	Location
FR	Injured registration data Triage Location

Source	Information
Agencies	FR status (unassigned, assigned task, on the way...) Vehicle status (unassigned/assigned to hospital...) Dispatch: Vehicles, person and injured assigned to each task
Command Post	Situational awareness: update of relevant information on the ground
Emergency Services	The first report on the incident comes from citizens or any agency. Incident status updates from the same sources

Table 2 - Information from actors to be shared between countries.

3. Agreements between the manufacturers of the command-and-control applications for the definition and standardisation of Valkyries Interoperability Framework (VIF), which will contain the data models, common semantics, and common business processes. Includes the following entities:
 - a. Incident definition, including status, location, and assigned tasks.
 - b. Task definition, including task status, task action location, assigned assets and people, and assigned victims.
 - c. Assets definition, including type, capacity, status, and location.
 - d. Staff definition, including their status and location.
 - e. Victims' definition includes vital information, location, status, and the registration and triage information carried out on them.
 - f. Agencies, as well as the people and assets each has.
4. Development of a mobile tool for FR teams that allows evolving from the manual paper registration model to having the data centralised, available and updated. Said tool is an application for iOS /android that has the following basic functionalities:
 - a. Registration of the data of the victims of the incident
 - b. Record of the triage carried out on the victims of the incident.
 - c. Geolocation report.
 - d. Reports monitoring each victim's evolution and management and medical data's evolution.

The tool is adapted to the Valkyries data model to facilitate the integration and sharing of the data acquired from the victims during the incident management.
5. Information integration mechanisms in the SIGRUN common interoperability platform. Using the already defined data model, an MQTT integration bus is enabled with different emission-subscription channels through which the information is shared. The channels that are initially proposed will be:
 - a. Incident information: creation and updates.
 - b. Tasks associated with the incident information.
 - c. Vehicle information: status and position information.
 - d. Staff information: status and position information.
 - e. Injured information: data about injured, triage data, status, and position.
6. Development of command-and-control tools changes to adapt them to interoperability mechanisms:
 - a. Creation of endpoints according to the channels (sender and receiver endpoints).

- b. Development of modules to transform and adapt the internal data model of each tool to the SIGRUN data model.
7. Creation of dashboards in the command-and-control tools that allow global monitoring and situational awareness for the incident, using own application data and received data from another country using SIGRUN integrations.

EVALUATE THE IMPACT

It is important to evaluate the impact to determine if the number of voice calls during emergency management has been reduced. The results can help identify areas that need improvement and allow you to adjust the solution to make it more effective.

5.4.3 Conclusions

The core of the opportunity is about standardising the data models, adapting the C2 tools to connect them to the interconnectivity platform, and developing an application that allows the FRs to share the information with the rest of the actors. This will require great effort and coordination by all the parties that are going to intervene, but the impact on emergency management will be very beneficial.

Guidelines: The applications to be developed should be designed to be highly useful because if they are ineffective, conventional tools will continue to be used.

The integration of automated task systems (process workflows), integration with logistics systems and incident information in the own Command and Control system reduces manual work. Command and Control systems must have external interfaces to include or incorporate these functionalities into the tool.

Lessons learnt: Applications that are developed to reduce communications for FRs and enable data capture must be robust to loss of communications and allow for offline data synchronisation and operation at reduced bandwidths.

Even if applications are developed to reduce voice communication and ensure the availability of communications, if the interoperability of the applications with the C2 application is not ensured, it will not be easy to achieve an integrated system that enables agile decision-making.

There may be reluctance on the part of FRs to share sensitive or security-related data, but a legal framework must be ensured, and applications must be designed according to this legal framework.

5.5 CO.WP4.55: Use of wearables to support triage

This sub-chapter presents the opportunity CO.WP4.55 related to using wearables in triage procedures as an opportunity for SWOT analysis and approach followed in VALKYRIES.

5.5.1 SWOT evaluation

The use of wearable devices to support triage from first responders, as of today, was restricted within the safe area of operations of first responders, leaving a huge gap in victims' traceability from the point they were rescued or found by non-medical first responders up to the delivery to medical or paramedical personnel carrying on triage procedures. Because of this perception, technologies supporting triage developed so far focus mainly on non-wearable sensors transmitting vital signs or other related data to the nearest hospital or Command and Control of EMS, respectively.

Another reason for not introducing wearable technologies so far for victim tracking /tracing and monitoring is the lack of common standards on communication protocols and data sets from sensors used to support triage procedures. As it is then logically expected, the use of wearables to track, trace and monitor victims in disasters that do not need hospitalisation or other medical treatment as part of triage has not yet been developed. So, no common standards or harmonised procedures have been introduced to support such victims' traceability, monitoring, and management when they are handled to public services after their evacuation for assistance, housing/hospitality and other related services (usually by Red Cross, Municipalities or Volunteers NGOs).

The system architecture of SIGRUN, introduced in the VALKYRIES project, allows the secure and GDPR-compliant exchange of data between different agencies acting as first responders or as support organisations to evacuate victims straightforwardly. Using wearable devices acting as smart tags and ordinary smartphones or tablets, victims can be registered uniquely from the point of rescue to the total handling circle by authorities, the medical system included. As such wearable non-battery-operated devices use passive methods (RFID or NFC) to communicate to a smart device, then the complexity due to the lack of protocols, minimum data sets, etc., from the manufacturing side is moved to the flexible environment of modern telecommunication devices such as smart phones or tablets through the use of apps supporting the needed functionality to support triage.

Using the same approach, ready out-of-self-commercial products such as sensors embedded in smart clocks can trace first responders' vital signs, and geolocation based on the standard functionality smart phone/mobile technology provides today.

6.4.2 Strengths

1. Wearable devices have become widely used. Such wearable devices, such as smart clocks, if tagged in a simple, low cost and easy-to-use way, create the general framework of people's acceptance of wearing wearables during triage procedures.
2. They possess several potentially very useful functions in MCI (e.g., geolocation, vital parameters, messaging). The functionality provided by other mobile telecommunication devices, such as smart phones or tablets, takes advantage of functions supported (such as geolocation, time stamps, apps etc.) to link wearables such as smart clocks functionality/censoring into the triage procedure, even when advanced triage MCI systems are not available.
3. Generally long-life battery. As power is unnecessary for smart tags and clocks to operate short-distance communications (usually via Bluetooth protocols), wearables such as smart tags or alternative vital sign sensors consume less power, usually enough to cover several days within a disaster management circle.
4. Low cost and easy to maintain.

6.4.3 Weaknesses

1. Different technologies of various devices and data accessibility. Typical wearables supporting vital triage sensing available today do not follow any commonly accepted standard in data or communication.
2. Possible poor data quality due to sensor calibration defects. In all cases, using wearables to support triage based on specially designed equipment/sensors is more accurate for medical peruses. As such devices need to maintain and calibrated quite often, their accuracy is lost if no proper maintenance protocols are followed

3. Medical personnel trust only devices from medical equipment manufacturers, which have not been designed or equipped with any technology or method for personalisation of data from the one wearing them.

6.4.4 Opportunities

1. The use of wearables as a common standard for tracking, tracing, and monitoring victims in a disaster expands first responders' effectiveness in saving lives.
2. A unique way to register victims that need triage handling or not.
3. Protection of sensitive medical personal data of a victim to SIGRUN architecture (logging data in blockchain cryptographically, secured access to data only to authorised personnel, on a need-to-know basis). As so, GDPR-related Guidelines are followed.
4. Create a standard for handling refugees of any type using wearable smart tag devices for registration and access to services.
5. Introduction of IoT and Satellite IoT available technologies either to support victim's tracking, tracing and monitoring or first responders' rescue vehicles or equipment using the same concept and technologies.
6. Improve the reliability of detected vital parameters by achieving a standard equivalent to medical devices. This would allow these data to be used for large-scale automatic monitoring functions, such as by expert systems.

5.5.1.1 Threats

1. Acceptance by medical or paramedical personnel and Authorities
2. Bioethical issues
3. Low acceptance or resists from the classic wearables manufacturers and industry.

5.5.2 Scope of VALKYRIES approach

Valkyries SIGRUN architecture allows alternative sensing devices or technologies to support the first responders' mission, triage procedures on victims included.

PROCESS ANALYSIS AND PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

The first step is to analyse the current situation and understand why wearables are not used today in rescue during disasters to support triage or other crucial functions. The following factors are identified:

1. Lack of industry's common standards. As every company producing sensors in triage support uses property protocols or data sets, exchanging such information between agencies in multicausality disaster events is difficult to impossible.
2. Lack of alternative communication channels: if the people involved in resolving the emergency don't have access to the means to obtain or report information, they surely resort to voice calls to obtain and report information or help.
3. Training of the civilian population on how to handle emergency situations: if the civilian population does not have a public means to receive information or does not know how to use the available resources to obtain said information, they will resort to voice calls as the main source of information.

STRATEGY TO ADDRESS THE OPPORTUNITY

There are various strategies to reduce voice calls during emergency management between the different actors involved, considering the factors exposed in the previous section.

One of the main objectives should be to improve the availability and accuracy of the information in emergency management. The following possible solutions should be considered:

1. Share information between agencies of the different countries involved in the emergency to improve the coordination of actions to manage the incident. Cooperative work between countries and sharing information and resources helps to obtain a complete picture of the situation and make more effective decisions.
2. Collect information on the ground from Ground 0 to the handling a hospital of victims in almost real-time (such as the status of the injured, the situation of assets and people, or information on the progress of the cause of the natural disaster) and have it in the IT systems available and shared by the agencies and authorities, helps identify the most affected areas and direct resources more effectively.
3. Establishment of clear and standardised protocols for data handling and exchange through the Valkyries SIGRUN architecture.
4. Mobile applications that allow information to be shared in real time between field staff and coordination and response teams can also be used to track, trace and manage victims.
5. Unique and simple registration of victims from ground 0 with all available (not medical information) gathered or changed with full transparency. Such gathered information gathered by non-medical first responders registering a victim, such as demographical info, a photo of the victim and a photo of the rescue scene, are usually vital for triage handling when the victim is passed to EMS/medical professionals.
6. Information gateways allow the automatic integration of the updated and real-time position of the victims or the vehicles through GIS/Galileo systems to know the location and situation of all victims and assets on the ground and coordinate the assignment of pending dispatch tasks.
7. Standardisation of the data model allows interoperability, and it is feasible to share and use them between different systems and organisations so that they can be compatible after a transformation process with the applications used for management command and control.

ACTION PLAN

The steps to be followed that make up the action plan are described:

1. Create a global scheme on the information that can be shared between the actors and countries that allows more efficient emergency tracking, tracing and management of victims supporting triage with the use of wearable devices bringing into real life combined technologies such as smart tagging, IoT, mobile or satellite technologies and sensors.
2. Proof of concept using the above combination of technologies based on wearables supporting victim triage in different uses/scenarios within the Valkyries project.
3. Use of wearables to support evacuated victims tracking, tracing and management.
4. Use of wearables as a tagging device in cooperation with other triage supporting technologies such as TASICA's.
5. Use wearables as an alternative triage supportive mechanism, where other triage IT systems are unavailable.
6. Use wearables as part of a Satellite IoT method for tracking vehicles or responders' vitals and geolocation (wearables embedded in first responder's jacket)

7. Create a first consensus from at least one EU country to primarily accept such a method to support triage as a pre-standards.
8. Publish the evidenced measurable results from Valkyries UCs testing this opportunity against the non-use of wearables or traditional methods to support triage.

5.5.3 Conclusions

The core of the opportunity is about standardisation and harmonisation of the technological chain that supports the usage of wearables using different types of technologies (such as smart tagging, IoT, mobile or satellite communications, geolocation and sensors) in assisting victims supporting triage procedures before and after victim's handling to medical/paramedical professionals. To optimise the global response, better manage the medical support and response to victims, and protect sensitive personal information, the SINGRUN architecture is a must. The benefits of using wearables as a standard during disasters are also creating a major opportunity for EU industries on sensors, IoT and space technologies to advance against their competition. Therefore, a common semantic and taxonomy should be standardised; the key technological artefacts and components should be interoperable; and the location or vital signs data sharing mechanisms should be standardised in a common data model and a common framework, including the API to existing systems or Apps supporting victims management and handling, should be established.

5.6 CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

The opportunity to analyse historical data from missions and platforms aims to analyse data from past emergencies and identify patterns that will help to improve the action plan when an emergency happens again. To do this, collecting different data from past disasters and from the platforms that FRs use to send information about patients is necessary. This way, a dataset containing this information can be generated, and artificial intelligence techniques can be used to predict past events and act more quickly.

5.6.1 SWOT evaluation

This SWOT analysis identifies the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats that need to be considered to carry out the historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.

5.6.1.1 Strengths

1. In emergency response, time is of the essence, which is why using predictive analysis to calculate potential risks and develop better plans for disaster management is crucial. By analysing data from various sources, predictive analysis can help emergency responders anticipate potential disasters and develop better effective strategies to mitigate them.
2. In an emergency response situation, information is critical to make informed decisions quickly. In mass casualty incidents (MCIs), large amounts of data must be collected, analysed, and shared in real time. Different drills are conducted to improve emergency response operations, and data is collected from these exercises to generate a dataset containing all this information.
3. One of the key benefits of generating a dataset from real MCIs and drills is that it can train emergency responders and help them make better decisions in high-pressure situations. By analysing the data and identifying commonalities, emergency responders can better understand the situation, including the scope of the emergency and the resources required.
4. Evaluating the effectiveness of previous emergency responses is a critical aspect of emergency management. It allows organisations to identify areas of strength and

weakness in their response strategies and make improvements to better prepare for future emergencies. One way to evaluate the effectiveness of previous emergency responses is through historical data analysis from missions and platforms.

5. Historical data analysis can be a powerful tool for sharing knowledge and best practices across different emergency response organisations and agencies. By analysing data from past emergencies, teams can gain valuable insights into improving their collective response capabilities and better collaborate during future emergencies.

5.6.1.2 Weaknesses

1. Data collection from some platforms can be challenging. This can be due to limited data storage capabilities, security concerns, and incompatibility issues. In certain emergency response scenarios, data may be collected using technologies or platforms not designed to store large amounts of data. This can make it difficult to obtain comprehensive data sets for analysis. Additionally, data security concerns may limit the availability of certain data sets for analysis, especially in cases involving sensitive personal information.
2. Processing of the data is necessary to adapt it to the dataset. This process involves several steps that help ensure that the data is standardised, organised, and formatted in a suitable way for analysis.
3. One of the challenges is the quality of the data. In situations where the emergency response system is not well-established, the data may have low quality, which can impact the accuracy and reliability of the analysis.
4. Historical data may be biased towards certain emergencies, leading to incorrect conclusions and recommendations. By taking a comprehensive approach to data collection and analysis, being transparent about the limitations of the analysis, and using advanced data analysis techniques, emergency response teams can minimise the effects of bias and ensure that their conclusions and recommendations are based on accurate and reliable data.
5. This analysis can be a complex process that requires a high level of expertise in data analysis to ensure that the data is properly processed and analysed to extract meaningful insights.

5.6.1.3 Opportunities

1. Improving coordination and communication between emergency responders is essential for effective historical data analysis in emergency response operations. By establishing clear protocols, using common tools and methods, building strong relationships, and leveraging technology, emergency responders can collaborate more effectively and generate meaningful insights from their data.
2. Invest in new platforms and technologies that can enhance emergency response capabilities. By leveraging emerging technologies such as geographic information systems (GIS), real-time data collection and analysis, Internet of Things (IoT), communication technologies, and new emergency response technologies, emergency responders can improve their ability to respond to emergencies effectively and efficiently, reducing the impact of disasters and saving lives.
3. Creating expert systems that predict the evolution of ongoing accident scenarios can significantly enhance emergency response capabilities and historical data analysis from the missions and platforms. By training these systems on historical data, they can learn to recognise the key factors that contribute to the evolution of an accident scenario, such as weather conditions, the spread of fire, and the movement of people and

vehicles. Once trained, expert systems can be used to analyse real-time data and predict the likely evolution of an ongoing accident scenario.

4. Implement and validate a decision-making algorithm that, based on past data, can size the need for resources to be deployed from the earliest stages of the event.

5.6.1.4 Threats

1. Emergencies are unpredictable and constantly changing scenarios. Therefore, emergency response teams need to be able to adapt to new situations quickly, even if it means deviating from the data analysis generated by historical data. Sometimes, taking action solely based on historical data analysis may result in inadequate or ineffective emergency response. It is important to remember that historical data analysis can only provide a snapshot of past events and cannot account for all the unique circumstances and variables of a current emergency.
2. Protecting sensitive information is important for historical data analysis in emergency response. In many cases, emergency response data can contain personal information, such as names, addresses, and medical information, that must be kept confidential to protect the privacy of those involved. Emergency response teams must follow strict data security protocols to protect sensitive information. This may include using encryption technologies, limiting access to the data, and ensuring that all data is stored securely.
3. The security of historical data is critical for emergency response teams. Cyber-attacks, data breaches, and other security risks can compromise the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of the data, potentially leading to serious consequences for emergency response operations.

5.6.2 Scope of VALKYRIES approach

The process of analysing historical data from missions and platforms in emergencies involves several steps that must be followed to obtain a dataset containing the necessary information to be able to analyse it and, in the future, employ artificial intelligence techniques to identify trends that will help the FRs to act more quickly and effectively. The key steps in this process are detailed below.

1. Analyse and compare the existing datasets in the literature: First, it is necessary to study the existing ones to see what problem they are trying to solve and their scope. To do this, it is necessary to analyse whether these existing datasets solve problems such as the study of patients' evolution, data collection from existing platforms, ways of acting in the face of a given emergency, etc. Furthermore, for each dataset in the literature, the size of the data used, i.e., the number of rows in the dataset, the number of features used and which ones are the most important, must be analysed. Moreover, it is necessary to know the experience of the FRs from Valkyries to see if these datasets are effective and can be used to create their own dataset with data obtained during the use cases.
2. Obtaining data from existing datasets: Once the different datasets have been studied, we must generate a dataset containing the data analysed in the previous step. As each dataset may contain a different format, it is necessary to carry out a step called data integration, consisting of formatting the data so that the generated dataset contains all the information with the same structure.
3. Data collection from use case 1 in Valkyries project: In the use case 1, a fire drill will be carried out on the border between Spain and Portugal and the SIGRUN platform will be

used in this drill. On this occasion, the data obtained in the drill will be collected and added to the generated dataset.

4. Data cleaning: Once the dataset contains all the data, a data cleaning step needs to be performed to contain quality data. The following techniques can be used for this purpose:
 - a. Missing data: A dataset containing missing data can lead to several problems, such as loss of efficiency, complications when analysing the data, or even lead to biases in the resulting models. If the data comes from a database, missing data is usually represented as null. To solve this problem, the first option is to do nothing, the second is to remove those attributes with null values, the third is to remove the total object, and finally to replace the gap with a value, either a constant or a value that preserves the mean or variance for numeric data or the mode for nominal data.
 - b. Noise data: Noise is when there is a random error or variance in a measurement of a variable. Several methods can be used to eliminate this noise, such as discretisation, which consists of smoothing a set of ordered values by consulting their neighbourhood; regression, a regression process is carried out to adjust the function and replace the values with those predicted by the function; clustering, which allows outliers to be identified.
 - c. Variables with variance close to zero: in many situations, variables may have only one value (zero variance variables). This can cause models to exhibit unstable behaviour. On the other hand, there may also be variables where a value occurs with a low frequency, i.e. variables with variance close to zero. Therefore, these variables can be eliminated, as they will not contribute anything interesting to the analysis.
5. Data transformations: Data transformation techniques allow the data to be prepared appropriately to apply various data mining techniques. Some techniques can be seen below:
 - a. Data normalisation: The basic idea is to scale the values of a variable to a given range. Some techniques require the data to be normalised. Some normalisation methods are min-max normalisation, z-transform normalisation, or decimal scaling normalisation.
 - b. Discretisation: The conversion of a numerical value into an ordered nominal value. This step is performed because some techniques only accept discrete attributes, also when there are certain significant thresholds or when the interpretation of the scale is not linear. The most used techniques are entropy-based discretisation, interval fusion by analysis, histogram, or cluster analysis.
 - c. From categorical to numerical variables: Some techniques can manipulate categorical data, and others can only handle numerical variables. For this, techniques such as ordinal encoding, One-Hot encoding, or encoding by dummy variables can be used.
6. Analysis of the resulting dataset: Once the previous stages have been completed, an artificial intelligence model could be generated, specifically machine learning (ML), capable of predicting the demand for emergency services in different areas and times, identifying high-risk areas, since historical data analysis can identify high-risk areas where emergencies are most likely to occur; prediction of response times; or

identification of trends in emergency response data over time, to enable emergency personnel to develop more effective strategies for responding to emergencies.

5.6.3 Conclusions

Having access to historical data can greatly improve emergency response efforts. By analysing past missions and platforms, emergency responders can identify patterns and trends that can help them better anticipate and respond to future emergencies. For example, historical data analysis can help emergency responders identify areas particularly vulnerable to certain types of disasters, allowing them to prioritise resources and plan accordingly.

Well-defined traditional methodologies for data analysis have been applied, demonstrating that it is feasible to apply them in a unified and harmonised way, potentially in Europe in the future. Although it takes some time for adoption, as the technology is mature, it is easy to extend.

Guidelines: When analysing historical data for emergency response, it's essential to clearly understand what you want to achieve and identify specific metrics to measure success. You should collect data consistently and ensure it's high-quality, properly cleaned, and pre-processed. Select appropriate statistical methods and algorithms to analyse the data and communicate the findings to stakeholders and decision-makers clearly and concisely.

Lessons learnt: Collaboration and coordination between different agencies are crucial for successful emergency response. By working together and sharing data and resources, emergency responders can enhance their efforts and avoid duplicating their work. Historical data analysis has also shown that it's essential to remain flexible and adaptable to the unique circumstances of each emergency to provide a targeted response.

5.7 CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs

This sub-chapter presents CO.WP4.2 related to logistics assistance using UAVs as an opportunity for SWOT analysis and approach followed in VALKYRIES.

5.7.1 SWOT evaluation

The use of UAVs has huge potential in disaster relief operations throughout Europe. The user has already started, but it is a way to go for them to be a common tool in Europe. In recent years, the use of drones in the search for missing persons during natural disasters and major emergencies has become increasingly specialised and consolidated, involving numerous rescue organisations such as Mountain Rescue, the Fire Brigade, Civil Defence and the Red Cross. Some drones have night vision systems or high-definition cameras that enable them to locate people in distress, even in poor visibility conditions. In addition, wireless and satellite communication technologies allow drones to exchange information in real-time with rescue teams in the field, providing an up-to-date picture of the situation and improving the coordination of rescue operations. The SWOT looks at the possibility of making UAVs an integral and common part of the toolbox for first responders in disaster relief operations.

5.7.1.1 Strengths

1. UAVs are cheaper to procure and operate than aircraft and helicopters.
2. Can respond and arrive in the disaster area faster than the alternatives.
3. Not affected by clouds
4. It can carry a variety of sensors, enabling the collection of large amounts with different purposes simultaneously.

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5. It can give first responders detailed information on where to start and feed them with live updates.
 6. Can operate in a toxic environment.

5.7.1.2 Weaknesses

1. Need humans to monitor, control and coordinate.
2. Commercial UAVs have a limited number of sensors available.
3. Advanced UAVs are often heavy and bulky, making it difficult for first responders to carry them into the disaster area.
4. UAVs are still a relatively new technology; some first responders may lack the necessary training and experience.

5.7.1.3 Opportunities

1. Common European frequencies to operate and relay information will let UAVs operate in Europe, making it possible to lend equipment to disaster areas regardless of borders.
2. Specialised first responders UAVs can assist first responders in various tasks like logistics, Situational awareness, and control of humans. This will reduce the number of humans needed for these tasks, making them available for tasks not possible for UAVs to conduct.

5.7.1.4 Threats

1. The lack of a standardised UAV system can make operating cross-border or lending equipment from other organisations difficult.
2. Complex operation procedures of the UAVs will heighten the threshold for the first responders to use the equipment in a real disaster operation.
3. Multioperation UAVs are expensive, reducing the possibility for first responders to procure them.
4. UAVs may be vulnerable to cyberattacks or interference, limiting their ability to operate effectively.

5.7.2 Scope of VALKYRIES approach

The main challenges to using existing commercial solutions, in addition to the lack of standardisation, are the lack of expertise of the disaster relief organisations, the implementation and operational challenges, and cost and resource constraints. This is a challenge regarding the lack of expertise of operating organisations because unmanned systems solutions can be complex and require specialised knowledge and skills to design, implement and operate effectively. The main implementation challenge is integrating the unmanned system into the existing operation and properly testing the system before it is fully integrated. In addition, unmanned systems require effective operation and maintenance to function at peak performance and deliver the desired results. All this can be expensive and resource-intensive, and disaster relief organisations may not have the budget or manpower to do it effectively or want to prioritise other areas.

These challenges are overcome by the standardisation of products and technology development, where more user-friendly solutions are coming to the market every year. However, disaster relief organisations wait. Even though there are challenges to using unmanned systems in disaster relief, integrating such systems to these operations must continue to steadily grow, as mastering this technology for life-saving is already proven beneficial.

The VALYRIES project will highlight the possibilities of unmanned systems in disaster relief. This was mapped together with possible products which are already in the market. This map can be used to sort the different areas and operations regarding the level of existing standardisation and the need for more. Some of these possibilities will be demonstrated in the User Cases.

The final step is to see if the different solutions can be fed into and presented with the SIGRUN platform. This will show the need for standardisation and possible solutions to this.

5.7.3 Conclusions

Many types of unmanned systems can be used in a disaster relief area. Unmanned Aerial Systems are, at the moment, the most common, but there are commercial Unmanned Ground Vehicles (rovers) and unmanned surface vehicles (drone ships) for the first responders. The main issue is the standardisation and harmonisation of the operation- systems and procedures. This is vital to secure the possibility of unmanned systems operations in the whole of Europe cross-borders and organisations. A common training program is needed to secure a low threshold for first responders to use the systems, and this also emphasises the need for standardisation. A final area is an economy. It should be developed at a basic level that an unmanned system must be able to conduct to be first responder approved. This should emphasise a low total price for both purchase and operation. Add on should be with a standardised connecting system and open source operating system to secure competition between the producers.

Lessons learnt: There are discrepancies between what producers integrate into their unmanned systems to solve first responders' needs and what the first responders feel they need, especially considering the amount of available funding for procurement, time for training, and competence building, where the use of unmanned systems will steal time from actual first aid and triage training.

6. Conclusions

Although there are different levels of technological maturity, it is expected that by 2029 it might be sensible to think that these opportunities, which are the most relevant in impact and feasibility, could end up being a standard at the European level. The prioritisation of these opportunities at the EU level is essential as they represent current issues that emergency agencies face. Thus, the standardisation of these opportunities would greatly benefit emergency services to make them work better, resulting in improved citizenship as more lives could be saved.

7. Annex A – References and bibliography

1. **Consortium, VALKYRIES.** *Deliverable D2.7 "Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases.* 2022.
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8. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
COP	Common Operational Picture
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IOT	Internet of Thing
MCI	Mass Casualty Incident
VIF	Valkyries Interoperability Framework

Table 3 - Glossary